

IMMUNOCORRECTIVE THERAPY IN THE TREATMENT OF PATIENTS
WITH CHRONIC PYELONEPHRITIS

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The actuality of the issue.

Chronic pyelonephritis in the structure of extragenital pathology in pregnant women occupies a leading position due to the high prevalence, complicated course of pregnancy and childbirth. Chronic pyelonephritis (CP) triggers a whole cascade of reactions, primarily immune, at the systemic and local level. In CP of pregnant women, the role of the immune system lies not only in the pathological process occurring in the kidneys, but also takes into account a number of changes in the restructuring of the immune system of the pregnant woman. In connection with the above, the study of the role of the immune system of pregnant women with chronic pyelonephritis is of great interest.

Purpose of the study.

The purpose of the study was to study the effectiveness of immunocorrective therapy in the complex treatment of patients with chronic pyelonephritis.

Material and methods.

43 pregnant women with CP were examined, mean age 28.3 ± 0.2 years. The study included clinical research methods (survey, questioning, physical examination). From laboratory methods - a general analysis of blood, urine, urinalysis according to Nechiporenko, a tank. urine culture, biochemical blood tests and instrumental (ultrasound) research methods. Cellular immunity was studied by the method of monoclonal antibodies. Humoral immunity was studied by the Mancini immunodiffusion method.

Among the examined women, the first group consisted of pregnant women (n=14) receiving traditional therapy. The second group of 13 pregnant women with CP received ozone therapy against the background of traditional therapy (basic treatment + 400 ml of saline solution ozonated to an ozone concentration in the liquid of 4 mg/l, intravenously, drip). The third group of 15 pregnant women with CP - with traditional therapy received ozone therapy and immunocorrective therapy with polyoxidonium.

Results of the study.

The characteristics of clinical and laboratory data during therapy showed significant changes, so back pain decreased by 85.71%, 92.31% and 93.33%, respectively, both in the first, second and third groups. Indicators such as dysuria decreased by 92.85%, 92% and 93% (respectively in the first, second and third groups). Leukocyturia significantly decreased on the fifth day by 71.43%, 84.62%, 86.67% (in the first, second and third groups, respectively). The results of eradication indicators of pathogens after treatment in combination with traditional therapy with ozone and immunocorrective therapy were

significantly better than in the group with ozone therapy against the background of traditional therapy and in the traditional treatment group (86.6%, 84.6% and 64.28% respectively).

As a result of the study, before the treatment of patients, significant decreases in cellular immunity, in particular CD3, CD4 and CD8, were revealed, and a significant increase in IgA, IgM was revealed. After the treatment in the treatment group in combination with traditional therapy with ozone and immunocorrective therapy, significant increases in the number of CD3, CD4 and CD8 (by 76.1%, 64.68% and 58.3%, respectively) were revealed, compared with the group of women who received only ozone therapy against the background of conventional therapy and in the conventional treatment group (66.23%, 59.54%, 54.2% and 61.12%, 54.68%, 51.4%, respectively), and there were also normalization of immunoglobulins A and M was noted.

Conclusions.

Along with the improvement of clinical and laboratory data in pregnant women with CP, normalization of cellular and humoral immunity parameters was noted. An additional appointment to the traditional therapy of chronic pyelonephritis of pregnant women, ozone therapy and immune system correction therapy, is a more effective way of treatment.